

In Silico 3D Simulations of Atrial Fibrillation Mechanisms

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Abstract— Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most common sustained cardiac arrhythmia in clinical practice, with a significant impact on patients' quality of life. In recent decades, clinical research has made considerable progress in seeking to understand the triggering and maintaining mechanisms of AF. With this progress, cardiac electrophysiology simulations have gained prominence in basic cardiology research. In this context, the present study aims to simulate the main mechanisms of AF on a 3D surface of the right atrium, including Ectopic Foci, Rotors, and Multiple Reentries. The openCARP (open-source simulator) was used, with the Courtemanche mathematical model for atrial cells and the monodomain model to represent the communication between myocardial cells in electrical activity. The simulations were visually classified using the openCARP Meshalyzer tool. Furthermore, qualitative analyses were performed, including observations of the wavefront morphology, initial conditions generating the mechanism, transmembrane potential signal shape, and patterns in fibrotic regions. Comparative analysis between some simulations was also addressed. In summary, these simulations support the theories of the simulated AF mechanisms and may uncover underlying patterns of arrhythmic conditions, providing insights for the study and understanding of this disease, with potential applications in clinical practice and future *in silico* studies.

Keywords — Atrial Fibrillation, Computational Simulations, Arrhythmia Mechanisms, Mathematical Models of Cardiac Cells.

I. Introduction

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most common cardiac arrhythmia found in clinical practice, affecting 1% of the world's population, with increasing rates to 9% for octogenarians [1]. AF incidence in Brazil is around 0.5% of the general population [2].

In AF, the electrical activity is “chaotic” affecting the atria to pump blood effectively, contributing to thromboembolic complications [3]. AF has emerged as an important public health problem in the last twenty years, demanding considerable health resources [4]. Its profound impacts on quality of life are evident, mainly due to its clinical consequences, such as cognitive changes [4].

Therefore, studies aiming to improve the current knowledge on AF, its mechanisms and therapy, would be of great importance, which can later improve the quality of life of patients.

The initiation and maintenance mechanisms of AF have not been completely clarified, and there are controversies [1].

Currently, three main mechanisms are responsible for the triggering and maintenance the AF: focal activity, rotor, and multiple continuous intra-atrial reentries [1].

The theory of the ectopic focus mechanism is that AF is triggered by rapid firing of a single or multiple ectopic foci [5], competing with the SA node activity, and potentially triggering fibrillation. These foci can be found predominantly in the pulmonary veins, but also in the posterior wall of the left atrium, along the crista terminalis in the right atrium, in the coronary sinus, vena cava, and in the ligament of Marshall [4].

The rotor mechanism was established in 1978 [6], defined as a stable rotating pattern of reaction and diffusion, where the wavefront rotates around a central point known as a “singularity point”. According to Panagiotis et al. (2021) [7], this core (i.e singularity point) is almost unexcitable, and the front of the circulating rotor reach its tail, providing a 2π rad distance between subsequent action potentials, considering its duration cycle. In other words, while the wavefront is in the depolarization phase of the action potential, the cells located on the tail area are at the repolarization phase from the previous beat.

Our research group showed that rotors sometimes are spatiotemporal unstable either in invasive electrograms [8] or non-invasively, through the body surface mapping [9]. The formation of rotors can occur in remodeled cardiac tissue, for instance, by the wavefront propagation of an electrical impulse through a media with a conduction barrier, either anatomic or a fibrotic region [7].

Multiple reentries can be classified as a complex and disorganized series of multiple meandering wavefronts that merge and collide without forming an identifiable singularity point [10]. One of the crucial factors in reentry formation is the wavelength, resulting from the relationship between the refractory period and the conduction velocity [11]. When this wavelength shortens, more tissue area becomes available outside the refractory period, making allowing depolarization and contributing to the development of reentries [12].

In recent decades, basic and clinical research, along with the study through mathematical models of cardiac electrophysiology, have enabled great advances in the improvement of the diagnosis and treatment of various arrhythmias, even complex, as is the case of AF, having its mechanism gradually elucidated, but not fully clarified.

Computational models of atria [13], provides complementary information to those obtained with electrophysiological studies, helping to better understand the patterns of activation in both healthy and arrhythmic hearts, giving a much deeper interpretation of the experimental data.

These models can be used to understand arrhythmic mechanisms, validate therapies, test the results of interventions, and customize treatments. Despite the high quality of healthy heart models, the main challenges lie in the realistic representation of arrhythmic patterns and their mechanisms. In particular, the best way to reproduce the trigger and maintenance mechanisms, in the case of this project, of AF propagating in the three-dimensional geometry of the atria.

This study aims to simulate the main mechanisms of AF, focal activity, rotor, and multiple continuous intra-atrial reentries on a three-dimensional (3D) epicardial surface of the right atrium. The use of this computational approach allows an objective and precise analysis of these complex specificities and offers the advantage of controllable manipulation, overcoming the practical limitations of clinical research.

II. Materials and Methods

A. OpenCARP

The simulations of AF mechanisms were performed using the openCARP software, an open-source simulation platform. This tool offers the capability to perform cardiac electrophysiology simulations at levels ranging from individual cell scale to organ scale [14]. OpenCARP is equipped with the carputils framework, which allows configuring the simulation physiologic parameters using the Python programming language. Additionally, to visualize the data obtained after the simulations, the Meshalyzer tool, also part of openCARP, was used. All mechanisms were simulated on a Lenovo notebook, i5-1035G1, 8GB RAM.

B. Atrial Mesh

The mechanisms were simulated on a 3D epicardial surface of the right atrium composed of 64,266 vertices and 127,905 triangles (Figure 1). This mesh was constructed by Roney and colleagues [15] from high-resolution ex vivo diffusion tensor magnetic resonance imaging (DTMRI) data. From these segmented images, they created the simulation meshes, with an average edge length of 0.34 mm. Additionally, to represent the anisotropic effects caused by the organization of fibers in the tissue, each triangle was assigned the nearest DTMRI fiber from its midpoint, projecting it onto its surface.

Figure 1: Mesh of the right atrium used in the simulations. Anatomical

structures are indicated in the image: superior vena cava (SVC), inferior vena cava (IVC), right atrial appendage (RAA), and tricuspid valve orifice (TVO).

C. Mathematical Model of the Atrial Cell

The simulations were conducted using the Courtemanche model [13], as the basis for the mathematical representation of each cell in the atrium mesh. Courtemanche et al. developed a mathematical model based on data recorded from human atrial myocytes to describe the ionic currents that occur during the action potential (AP) in cardiac cells. In this model, the cell membrane is represented as a capacitor that accumulates charges, connected in parallel with resistors and batteries, where the ionic channels act as resistors and the batteries as driving forces.

The derivative of the membrane potential (V) with respect to time (t) is expressed by Equation (1):

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = \frac{-(I_{ion} + I_{st})}{C_m} \quad (1)$$

Where I_{st} is the stimulus current flowing through the membrane, I_{ion} is the sum of the main ionic currents (Equation 2), each with its specific ionic channel, and C_m is the membrane capacitance, a constant value of 100 pF:

$$I_{ion} = I_{Na} + I_{K1} + I_{to} + I_{Kur} + I_{Kr} + I_{Ks} + I_{Ca,L} + I_{p,Ca} + I_{NaK} + I_{NaCa} + I_{b,Na} + I_{b,Ca} \quad (2)$$

Additionally, in some simulations, a variant of the Courtemanche model was applied to represent the electrical remodeling caused by chronic AF, as developed by Loewe et al. [16]. In this model, I_{to} was reduced by 65%, I_{K1} was increased by 100%, I_{Ks} was increased by 100%, I_{Kur} was reduced by 50%, I_{CaL} was reduced by 55%, I_{NaCa} was increased by 60%, and the sarcoplasmic reticulum leakage current was increased by 50%. One of the significant differences between this variant and the original Courtemanche model is the refractory period, as the original model has a considerably longer refractory period, not favoring simulations of the AF mechanisms.

Figure 2 illustrates the AP of a simulated single cell with the Courtemanche model, and Figure 3 illustrates the AP of the Loewe variant, also simulated in a single cell.

Figure 2: AP curve for a cell modeled with the Courtemanche [13] model.

Figure 3: AP curve for a cell modeled with the Loewe [16] variant. From this figure, it is possible to observe that the refractory period is shorter for this variant compared to the original Courtemanche model.

D. Action Potential Propagation Model: Monodomain

Analyzing cells as separated units with the Courtemanche model allows them to be coupled to represent the electrical communication between myocardial cells [17]. The mathematical approach used to connect them and propagate the AP between the myocytes in the simulations was the monodomain model, in which the influence of the extracellular medium is disregarded, assuming that the extracellular anisotropy ratio and the intracellular anisotropy ratio are proportional, greatly reducing the computational cost for solving the numerical solutions [17]. The monodomain equation can be described as follows:

$$X \left(C_m \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + I_{ion}(V, \eta) \right) = \nabla \cdot (\sigma \nabla V) \quad (3)$$

Where V is the variable of interest, representing the transmembrane potential, σ is the conductivity tensor describing the electrical properties of the tissue, X is the surface-to-volume ratio of cardiac cells, C_m is the membrane capacitance, I_{ion} is the total density of ionic current, which is a function of V and a vector of state variables η , described by a system of differential equations to control the kinetics of the state variables of ionic channels, which switch between open and closed states depending on the potential, time, or ion concentrations [17].

E. Planar Wave Propagation

To simulate AP propagations in sinus rhythm, a planar wave simulation (PWS) was developed. In this simulation, a stimulus with a current density of $250 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ was applied to the sinus node region for 2 ms, at a frequency of 1.5 Hz. The simulation lasts for 3000 ms. The current density, frequency, and location of the sinus stimulus were kept the same in all simulations to maintain sinus activity. The Courtemanche model for the AP remained unchanged in terms of variables. The intracellular conductivity in the longitudinal (g_{il}) and transverse (g_{it}) directions of the fibers was set to 0.174 S/m. In the extracellular domain, the longitudinal (g_{el}) and transverse (g_{et}) conductivities of the were set to 0.625 S/m.

F. Ectopic Foci

For the ectopic foci, two simulations were performed, one with a single focus (EF1) and another with three foci (EF2).

The AP model used was the original Courtemanche model. The tissue conductivity was set to 0.174 S/m for g_{il}

and g_{it} and 0.625 S/m for g_{el} and g_{et} . The tissue stimulation protocol was defined with pacing from the sinus node and additional pacing(s) representing the ectopic focus(i), located near the crista terminalis, with a current density of $250 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, a frequency of 7 Hz, and a duration of 2 ms. Simulations EF1 and EF2 lasted 5000 ms.

G. Rotor

A total of six rotor simulations were performed. Two of them were carried out using the following method: A new region near the crista terminalis was created in the mesh using the Paraview software and a Python algorithm. In this region, the variant from the Courtemanche model developed by Loewe [16] was applied to represent the electrical remodeling caused by chronic AF, which promotes functional reentry and increases the substrate for AF due to the shortening of the wavelength. In this atrial region, the conductivity values were also decreased, with g_{il} and g_{it} equal to 0.08 S/m and g_{el} and g_{et} equal to 0.521 S/m, making the tissue with a higher incidence of anisotropy, favoring the occurrence of developing reentries. The sinus stimulus maintained its settings, and an ectopic stimulus was inserted in the crista terminalis region, with a frequency of 10 Hz, current density of $250 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, and a duration of 2 ms. Two variations of this simulation were performed, slightly changing the location of the ectopic focus (RS1 and RS2). RS1 lasted 3000 ms and RS2 lasted 4000 ms.

To simulate rotors with a higher stability, another method was employed: the Loewe's cellular mathematical model [16] was implemented throughout the atrium, and sinus rhythm was maintained. Unlike the other ectopic stimuli inserted in RS1 and RS2, in this case, three groups of cells on the anterior wall of the atrium were activated twice, with a frequency of 7 Hz, current density of $250 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, and duration of 2 ms. Simulations were conducted with different conductivities in the tissue, with g_{il} and g_{it} equal to 0.14 S/m and g_{el} and g_{et} equal to 0.7 S/m, multiplied by factors equal to 1 (RS3), 0.8 (RS4), 0.5 (RS5), and 0.3 (RS6). These simulations lasted 3000 ms.

H. Multiple Reentries

Three multiple reentry simulations were conducted using the same mechanism induction procedure. However, each simulation differed in considerations regarding fibrosis in the tissue. In the first simulation (MWS1), fibrosis was not considered. In the second simulation (MWS2), a fibrotic region was inserted in 15% of the atrial appendage and interatrial septum. Finally, in the third simulation (MWS3), a fibrotic region greater than 30% was added to the same regions of the atrial appendage and interatrial septum.

The method used to induce multiple reentries involved selecting four groups of cells distributed on the posterior wall of the atrium with spacing between them. The cell groups were stimulated simultaneously, but in each group, some cells were stimulated during the refractory period of their neighbors, while others were depolarized outside of this period. This was done to avoid the propagation of the wavefront in a planar manner, allowing the occurrence of multiple reentry circuits.

The Loewe's cell model [16] was used in all simulations. However, for MWS2 and MWS3, in addition to this variant that models the AP, another variant representing the effects caused by cytokines was used in the fibrotic regions of the appendage and interatrial septum [18].

The conductivity was set to 0.174 S/m for g_{il} and g_{it} , and 0.625 S/m for g_{el} and g_{et} , being multiplied by a factor of 0.3 in all simulations. However, in MWS2 and MWS3, the percentage of fibrotic elements had a very low conductivity of

10^{-7} S/m. The sinusoidal stimulus was maintained throughout the simulations, with the stimulus that depolarizes the four cell groups having a current density of $250 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, duration of 2 ms, and frequency of 8 Hz, triggering twice. Simulations MWS1, MWS2 and MWS3 lasted 5000 ms.

III. Results and Discussions

Visually, the simulated mechanisms were categorized based on their distinct morphological characteristics. Ectopic foci were identified by activations arising from a different region than the sinoatrial node, generating the propagation of a characteristic radial wave. In relation to rotors, a spiral-shaped structure with an almost unexcitable core was observed, and the wavefront velocity gradually decreased as it approached the center. On the other hand, in the multiple reentries, the collision of several wavefronts was observed, which, after collision, propagated in different directions.

Figure 4A shows a PWS representing a normal atrial rhythm, characterized by the absence of electrical remodeling of cells and fibrosis in the tissue. Figure 4B shows the EF1 simulation, where an ectopic focus is superimposed on the sinus stimulus and located at the crista terminalis. When analyzing the ectopic focus simulations, it was noted that, even with a focal firing frequency of 7 Hz, the tissue was not completely depolarized at the same frequency, due to the refractory period of the cells modeled based on the Courtemanche model. Additionally, Figure 5 reveals a shortening of the plateau phase of the AP, which is mainly responsible for the duration of the refractory period, possibly caused by the rapid activation frequency of the ectopic focus. This shortening of the refractory period is a factor that can increase the likelihood of AF events, such as reentries, which supports the well-known concept that AF can perpetuate itself, creating a self-reinforcing cycle (“AF begets AF”).

In the rotor simulations, the main underlying cause of the observed mechanism was wavefront block, resulting in the absence of radial propagation of the activation preceding the mechanism. Figure 4C (RS6 simulation) illustrates this block caused by the refractoriness of the surrounding tissue, which allowed the stimulus to propagate only in two distinct directions, giving rise to the formation of two rotors. Additionally, it was observed that the variant of the Courtemanche model [16], applied throughout the atrium (RS3, RS4, RS5, and RS6 simulations), sustained the mechanism for a longer period compared to the simulation in which this variant was applied only to a region on the anterior wall of the atrium (as in the RS1 simulation, illustrated in Figure 4D). This finding can be explained by the shortening of the refractory period present in this variant compared to the original Courtemanche model. Another differentiating aspect of these rotor simulations, which used different methods, was the organization of cell activation over time. RS1 and RS2 exhibited a more disorganized rhythm characteristic of AF compared to RS3, RS4, RS5 and RS6. Such a comparison can be made with Figure 6. A possible explanation for this disorganization is the presence of heterogeneity in the ionic and conductivity models in RS1 and RS2.

Figure 4: Representative simulations from AF mechanisms. This figure illustrates selected moments from different simulations, each demonstrating a distinct scenario. In A, the simulation of a planar wave PWS can be observed, while B presents the ectopic focus simulation EF1. In C, the rotor simulation RS6 is highlighted, followed by the rotor simulation RS1 in D.

Figure 5: Transmembrane potential signal (V_m) in mV from a cell in the EF1 simulation, where the decrease in the plateau is highlighted by the blue arrows.

Figure 6: Transmembrane potential signal (V_m) in mV for the rotor simulation RS1 above, and below, for the rotor simulation RS3. From the figure, it is possible to infer that in RS1, the cell activation pattern was more arrhythmic than in RS3.

The multiple reentry simulations followed a similar way to the rotor simulations in inducing the mechanism. By introducing more groups of cells to be stimulated and increasing the spacing between them, an increase in the occurrence of wavefront blocks was observed, resulting in the propagation of these waves in different directions instead of spreading radially. This scenario facilitated the induction of multiple reentries in diverse directions, as seen in Figure 7A and Figure 7B.

The greater distance between the groups of cells allowed that while one neighborhood of the group could not be depolarized after the group's activation due to conduction block caused by refractoriness, another neighboring region could be depolarized, encountering tissue outside the refractory period. This generated a small wavefront that propagated in a spiral and collided with other small wavefronts, generated in the same way, thus propagating multiple reentrant wavefronts.

In all three multiple reentry simulations, it was observed that the mechanism was only sustained for an extended period when there was a considerable number of initial wavefronts prior to the mechanism. In situations where the number of initial wavefronts was low, significant collisions between wavefronts did not occur to generate the multiple reentry pattern; instead, occasionally, rotors were formed.

Finally, in cases where a fibrotic region was inserted into the tissue (simulations MWS2 and MWS3), a distinctive pattern was identified in the AP signal at the edges of this region. Due to the prolonged refractory period present in the fibrotic area compared to the regions unaffected by fibrosis, this region could not depolarize at the same rate as the rest of the neighboring tissue during the arrhythmia. As a result, a signal with several small-amplitude peaks was observed, as can be visualized in Figure 8.

All simulations carried out can be viewed through the link:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLom9zID5FoVHx9UP8pEYvFX1tGW-feZxx>

Figure 7: Simulations from Multiple Reentries. A) A simulation that presents the multiple reentry simulation MWS1, and in B) the multiple reentry simulation MWS3.

Figure 8: Transmembrane potential signal (V_m) in mV for a cell located at the edge of the fibrous tissue in the MWS3 simulation.

IV. Conclusion

The present study used computational simulations to investigate the mechanisms underlying AF, a complex and clinically relevant cardiac arrhythmia. Through the visual categorization of the simulated mechanisms, it is possible to support the theories of ectopic foci, rotors, and multiple reentries as triggers for AF.

The analysis of ectopic focus simulations revealed that even with a relatively high firing frequency, the tissue was not completely depolarized due to the refractory period of cells based on the Courtemanche model. Additionally, there was a shortening of the refractory period of cells, which may increase the likelihood of AF events, such as reentries, reinforcing the well-known idea that “AF begets AF”.

In the rotor simulations, we found that the application of the Loewe's variant throughout the atrium sustained the mechanism for a longer period compared to applying this

variant in only a specific region. Furthermore, the presence of heterogeneity in ionic models and conductivity between different regions of the atrium may explain the greater disorganization and characteristic fibrillation pattern observed in some rotor simulations.

The multiple reentry simulations followed a similar logic than the rotor simulations in inducing the mechanism. The increase in the number of stimulated cell groups and the spacing between them facilitated the formation of multiple reentrant wave fronts, which are essential for establishing AF. Additionally, it was observed that the mechanism of multiple reentries was better simulated when a considerable number of wave fronts in different directions collided to give rise to the mechanism.

The insertion of a fibrotic region into the tissue caused changes in the propagation of electrical activation, resulting in small-amplitude peaks in the transmembrane potential signal at the edges of the fibrotic region. This electrophysiological response suggests that the presence of fibrosis affects local electrical conduction, contributing to the formation of arrhythmogenic patterns.

In short, our results demonstrate that computer simulations are a viable and valuable tool to investigate AF mechanisms, with enormous potential for research in cardiac electrophysiology. However, it is important to note that our conclusions are based on mathematical models and simplified simulations and therefore require further validation through quantitative, clinical studies and in vitro and in vivo experiments.

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